

Data analytics on the next generation e-learning engagement to the community of St. Dominic College of Asia

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Abstract

The purpose of the paper is to describe, introduce, and prescribe Edmodo as digital learning system to the basic and higher education in different schools, institutions, colleges, and universities in the global world. The study is about the assessment of an e-learning tool called Edmodo, designed for both basic and higher education as an additional teaching tool for educators. The main objective of the study is to evaluate the overall impression of Edmodo with all the features considering the functionality and the level of acceptance on both the basic and higher education factors. The descriptive research method, through UTAUT (Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology) Framework, is used, as it describes the nature of the situation as it exists at the time of the study. The E-Learning tool undergoes a series of testing and different assessments utilizing innovative assessment mechanisms as well as data mining approach.

Keywords: *Edmodo; E-learning; UTAUT Framework.*

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Introduction

E-learning is a new generation educational facility that shapes the present and future system of education. E-learning showcases the online delivery of instructional materials and support services to the students to support student proficiency and competency. Moreover, e-learning contributes to a positive learning attitude and study habits. The main intention of the study is to evaluate Edmodo, with the use of Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology, to cover the system's full potential in terms of cloud community and education (Testa & Tawfik, 2017).

E-learning systems play a significant role in the delivery of education due to the increasing usage of technological interventions in the field (Moore et al., 2011). Innovative learning technologies are now being incorporated into curriculum development and pedagogical activities due to a recent trend in education (Arkorful & Abaidoo, 2015). Even if planning and implementing e-learning is still difficult in some areas, it is a strategic choice for higher education globally. E-learning is generally understood to be a technology-supported process that has replaced or combined traditional teaching and learning techniques. It gives students new chances both on and off campuses (Tagoe, 2012).

In the Philippines, e-learning has several benefits both within and outside of the classroom. It enables communication between the student and the instruction (Bagarinao, 2015). Each students' individualized learning is improved. Its cost-effectiveness can be observed because it is thought to be affordable to reproduce and distribute educational materials (Smedley, 2010). Because of its novelty, the students can focus on engaging teachings, which makes them more motivated and open to suggestions (Kwofie & Henten, 2011). Since the computer enables the distribution of uniform information in a sequential manner based on the needs of the learners, whenever and wherever, the integrity of each lesson may be maintained.

To equip students with technology and ‘21st century skills’ like creative problem solving, a new model of education that involves revised curriculum, infrastructure, teacher professional development, textbooks, and exams has emerged. This model of education is known as e-learning and encompasses a wide range of content and instructional methods (Patterson et al., 2012). As a route for information exchange, it offers a promising answer. It is crucial to create accurate and reliable techniques of quality measurement and conduct comprehensive information quality evaluation because improved technologies may result in faster and easier access to information but do not always guarantee the quality of that information (Means et al., 2013).

Methodology

Model and Process

The UTAUT framework is used because it accurately captures the nature of the situation at the time the study was conducted. The following factors are considered:

- Student-Teacher Experience
- Mobility
- Scalability
- Social Collaboration
- Reporting Feedback and Analytics

Participants

The study involved the faculty members of St. Dominic College of Asia. The respondents are the study are the 75 faculty members both from the Higher Education and Basic Education Departments. Table 1 shows the profile of the faculty members.

Table 1. Faculty profile

Designation	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Higher Education Faculty	50	66.67	1
Basic Education Faculty	25	33.33	2
<i>Total</i>	75	100.00	

Instrumentation

The researchers used a questionnaire and was distributed to the faculty members of SDCA. The questionnaire consists of five (5) items in the functionality, four (4) items in mobility, four (4) items in scalability, four (4) items in social collaboration, and four (4) items in feedback and analytics. The following scales are used by the researchers in conducting the study for the evaluation and assessment of the e-learning tool, Edmodo. Below is the Likert scale that the proponents used:

Table 2. Assessment of student-teacher experience, mobility, scalability, collaboration, and analytics

Likert Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.51-4.50	Agree
3	2.51-3.50	Neutral
2	1.51-2.50	Disagree
1	1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree

Results

The generated data are tabulated and analyzed the functionality of our E-learning System built in Edmodo.

Table 3. Assessment on Edmodo faculty evaluation based on functionality

#	Functionality	Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
1	Edmodo was able to capture all student records accurately.	4.51	4	Strongly Agree
2	File attachment and distribution work properly.	4.55	3	Strongly Agree
3	Activity uploads and automatic checking work properly.	4.49	5	Agree
4	The application generates student grades correctly.	4.61	2	Strongly Agree
5	Generated printable reports produce accurate values.	4.78	1	Strongly Agree

The assessment on Edmodo Faculty Evaluation in terms of the functionality ranges the overall rate of 4.59. The result corresponds to a result of “Strongly Agree” based on the instrumentation used. Most of the faculty members “strongly agree” that generated printable reports produce accurate values (Mean = 4.78), the application generates student grades correctly (Mean = 4.61), file attachment and distribution work properly (Mean = 4.55), and Edmodo was able to capture all student records accurately (Mean = 4.51). Moreover, they “agree” that activity uploads and automatic checking work properly (Mean = 4.49).

Table 4. Assessment on Edmodo faculty evaluation based on mobility

#	Mobility	Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
1	The Edmodo portal is easy to access on any device.	4.78	1	Strongly Agree
2	The website design is simple and easy to navigate across different platforms.	4.66	2	Strongly Agree
3	Edmodo offers useful modules and features compatible on personal computer (PC) and mobile.	4.47	4	Agree
4	Pop-up messages and other labels are easy to understand across different platforms.	4.53	3	Strongly Agree

The assessment on Edmodo Faculty Evaluation in terms of the mobility ranges the overall rate of 4.61, corresponding to a verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree. Most of the faculty members “strongly agree” that the Edmodo portal is easy to access on any device (Mean = 4.78), the website design is simple and easy to navigate across different platforms (Mean = 4.66), and pop-up messages and other labels are easy to understand across different platforms (Mean = 4.53). Moreover, they “agree” that Edmodo offers useful modules and features compatible on personal computer (PC) and mobile (Mean = 4.47).

Table 5. Assessment on Edmodo faculty evaluation based on scalability

#	Scalability	Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
1	The Edmodo portal tests students’ capability in all subject matter.	4.78	1	Strongly Agree
2	Edmodo allows teachers to provide materials from student competency.	4.66	2	Strongly Agree
3	Edmodo offers useful modules and features that complies with the student assessment.	4.47	4	Agree
4	Edmodo provides features of monitoring students on aspects of learning competency.	4.53	3	Strongly Agree

The assessment on Edmodo Faculty Evaluation in terms of the scalability ranges the overall rate of 4.61, corresponding to a verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree. Most of the faculty members “strongly agree” that the Edmodo portal tests students’ capability in all subject matter (Mean = 4.78), allows teachers to provide materials from student competency (Mean = 4.66), and provides features of monitoring students

on aspects of learning competency (Mean = 4.53). Moreover, they “agree” that Edmodo offers useful modules and features that complies with the student assessment (Mean = 4.47).

Table 6. Assessment on Edmodo faculty evaluation based on social collaboration

#	Social Collaboration	Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
1	Edmodo allows teachers to communicate as well as students.	4.78	1	Strongly Agree
2	Edmodo builds social community that groups students and teachers for next generation learning management.	4.66	2	Strongly Agree
3	Edmodo offers useful modules and features compatible on personal computer (PC) and mobile.	4.47	4	Agree
4	Pop-up messages and other labels are easy to understand across different platforms.	4.53	3	Strongly Agree

The assessment on Edmodo Faculty Evaluation in terms of the social collaboration ranges the overall rate of 4.61, corresponding to a verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree. Most of the faculty members “strongly agree” that Edmodo allows teachers to communicate as well as students (Mean = 4.78), builds social community that groups students and teachers for next generation learning management (Mean = 4.66), and pop-up messages and other labels are easy to understand across different platforms (Mean = 4.53). Moreover, they “agree” that Edmodo offers useful modules and features compatible on personal computer (PC) and mobile (Mean = 4.47).

Table 7. Assessment on Edmodo faculty evaluation based on feedback and analytics

#	Feedback and Analytics	Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
1	Edmodo allows teachers to analyze student performance.	4.78	1	Strongly Agree
2	Edmodo builds analytics dashboard that monitors student performance.	4.66	2	Strongly Agree
3	Edmodo offers data for student assessment.	4.47	4	Agree
4	Graphs are provided in Edmodo to evaluate student participation on both individual and collaborative work.	4.53	3	Strongly Agree

The assessment on Edmodo Faculty Evaluation in terms of the feedback and analytics ranges the overall rate of 4.61, corresponding to a verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree. Most of the faculty members “strongly agree” that Edmodo allows teachers to analyze student performance (Mean = 4.78), builds analytics dashboard that monitors student performance (Mean = 4.66), and graphs are provided in the platform to evaluate student participation on both individual and collaborative work (Mean = 4.53). Moreover, they “agree” that Edmodo offers data for student assessment (Mean = 4.47).

Conclusion

The study used an alternative software evaluation method that includes the measurement and calibration of the user’s stress level in terms of software usage. The results also show that both higher and basic education teachers will greatly benefit in using E-Learning Management Systems as additional tool for teaching. The research also highlighted that software applications and other information systems should include the software usage burnout level to further determine the overall effectivity of a computerization project and its implementation. The consideration of assessing the overall system scope and functionality as well as its impact to the system user will lead to a better evaluation to determine the long-term success of a software project.

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